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CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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French Ambassador to Nigeria Wants CDA to Collaborate with Institutions in France

The French Ambassador to Nigeria, Mr. Jerome Pasquier has expressed readiness for French institutions to partner with the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) on agriculture and climate.

Mr. Pasquier was speaking at the Council Chamber of Bayero University shortly after touring facilities of the CDA and other buildings in the University. He said he was impressed with the huge investment made at the CDA and called for effective collaboration with French institutions.

He said the French Embassy in Abuja would do everything possible to fast track the collaboration aimed at improving food security and addressing climate change.

The French Ambassador also expressed determination to sign a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with Bayero University on health and security challenges.

The Envoy said he was instructed by the President of France when he visited Nigeria last year to develop collaborations with key partners including Universities and research centres. He said that Bayero University was one of those Universities the French government saw as an opportunity to make a long-term investment.

In his response, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, said the University has had a long-term relationship with France. He said that Bachelor of Arts French is one of the oldest programmes studied in the University, adding that

BUK had a number of activities with the French Embassy in Abuja. He added that the University has many students from French speaking countries.

“We are also aware that the French Embassy is working particularly on addressing the security challenges in Nigeria and other parts of West Africa. I want to inform his Excellency that in Bayero University, we are playing our part in trying to address those societal challenges.”

The Director, Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and that of Africa Centre of Excellence in Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP) made brief presentations on the programmes, objectives and activities of their centres.

The Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, said the focus of the centre was to specialize as a regional Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture delivering quality training and applied research in response to the needs of the West and Central Africa. He said the CDA engaged HCRERES to evaluate and accredit its programme, noting that it would be glad to collaborate with French Universities and research centres.

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BUK Wins ₦100m TRIMING Research Grant

Bayero University in collaboration with the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT) and the National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA) has won a three hundred and twenty-seven thousand two hundred and sixty-three dollars ninety-two cents \$327,263.92 (about N100m) Transforming Irrigation Management in Nigeria (TRIMING) research.

TRIMING is a World Bank project with counterpart funding from the Nigerian government under the Ministry of Water Resources. The objective of the project is to improve access to irrigation and drainage services and to strengthen institutional arrangements for integrated water resources management and agriculture service delivery in selected large-scale public schemes in Northern Nigeria which include: Bakolori Irrigation Scheme (BIS); Dadin Kowa Irrigation Scheme (DIS); Hadejia Valley Irrigation Scheme (HVIS); Kano River Irrigation Scheme (KRIS) and Middle River Valley Irrigation Scheme (MRVIS).

TRIMING is a World Bank project with counterpart funding from the Nigerian government under the Ministry of Water Resources

Bayero University as the lead institute on behalf of other collaborators signed a memorandum of Agreement (MoA) on 7th March, 2019 for the implementation of an Innovative Action Research in Kano River Irrigation Scheme titled: "Participatory Soil Salinity/Sodicity Management for Sustainable Crop Productivity under Irrigation and Improved Livelihood in Kano River Irrigation Project."

Present at the MoA signing ceremony were the National Project Coordinator of TRIMING, Engineer Peter Yakubu Manjuk and his team from Federal Ministry of Water Resources; BUK team led by Director, Academic Planning, Professor Bala Sidi Aliyu and a team of researchers, Research Panel of Experts (RPoE) led by Prof. Henry E. Igbadun and the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin.

CDA Participates at ACE Impact Boot Camp Workshop in Djibouti

A team from the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) participated at the Africa Centres of Excellence ACE Impact Bootcamp Workshop in the Republic of Djibouti from 19th – 21st February, 2019.

It would be recalled that the CDA-BUK had written a competitive proposal and eventually became successful as one of the new Centres to be funded by the World Bank under the ACE Impact Project along with 43 other centres from 12 West and Central African countries.

The objective of the Boot-camp Workshop was to provide participating Centers, their host institutions and governments the necessary tools to improve their readiness for the ACE Impact project implementation.

Towards achieving this, various sessions were held in which team members of the CDA-ACE implementation Team participated. The sessions were:

- Regional networking, to provide opportunities to form regional networks among participating Centers, kick starting groupings

and formulations of thematic network activities and expectations.

- Achieving basic and full readiness: Building Center Teams, Project Management and Governance.
- Developing the implementation plans built around the Vision of the Centres in wanting to stay relevant and financially stable beyond the end of the ACE impact project.
- Provide Centres with training

needed in communicating effectively the programmes they offer; their core strengths in research. (Pathway towards sustainability).

- Creation of teaching and research environments in line with international standards while leveraging ICT tools.

At the end of the 4 - day long workshop, the CDA ACE team members expressed zeal and optimism that the ACE Impact project would be a success just like the ACE I Project.

Members of the ACE Team who attended the workshop included Prof. J.M. Jibrin (Centre Leader / Director), Prof. S.G. Mohammed (Deputy Centre Leader, Training), Prof. Amina Mustapha (Monitoring and Evaluation Officer), U.G. Ohikere (Project Accountant), R.H. Sagagi (Procurement Officer) and Dr. Yusuf Garba (ACE Impact, Project Manager).

The Deputy Vice Chancellor (Administration), Professor Haruna Wakili, who represented the Vice Chancellor, Bayero University, Kano led the BUK-ACE delegation to the Djibouti event.

Minister of Environment Optimistic that CDA Farm Capable of Food Generation in Nigeria

The huge investment made at the Centre for Dryland Agriculture's ultra-modern research and commercial farm will significantly contribute to the food generation in Nigeria, according to the Minister of Environment, Sulaiman Hassan, who visited the farm and other facilities in the CDA.

"At this moment when food insecurity becomes increasingly challenging in Sub-Saharan Africa, such investment is absolutely required. What you are doing in the CDA will definitely increase the food generation in Nigeria and enhance the skills of farmers, as well as provide employment to a substantial number of people," said the Minister.

The Deputy Director Training of CDA, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed took the minister round the farm and other facilities in a tour led by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Academics, Professor Adamu Idris Tanko. The Minister, who saw the massive investment at the 15 hectare CDA Farm including the screen houses, said he had not seen such a facility in

any tertiary institution in Nigeria.

While at the Tissue Culture Laboratory, the Minister congratulated Bayero University for the huge investment in both the farm and the laboratories, saying that once farmers subscribe to the CDA projects, there would be more food in the country.

"The investment calls for more investment into this to achieve our target of food security considering

our huge population," said the Minister.

The Deputy Director, Research at the CDA, Dr Kabir Mustapha briefed the Minister that the Tissue Culture Laboratory was established to mass propagate crops that are important to farmers for distribution and try to address issues of conservation because there are a number of trees becoming extinct so this facility was set up to mass propagate the crops and put back to the environment.

He said another important issue for the establishment of the laboratory is that there are a number of important medicinal plants that have lots of values and they yield a number of chemical compounds which are very important for use in the pharmaceutical industries. He explained that the facility could develop protocols to produce those compounds in large quantities for pharmaceutical industries to benefit with faster production of the drugs they require.

CDA Organizes Workshop on Innovative University Teaching

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) conducted a workshop on **Innovative University Teaching** in collaboration with the Department of Science Education, University of Copenhagen, Denmark between Monday, 25th March, 2019 and Saturday, 30th March, 2019. The workshop was aimed at equipping and enabling the participants drawn from various departments of the university to motivate and raise the capacity of fellow staff to reform their approach to teaching and learning.

The training was in tune with the University's Quality Assurance Policy, whose mission statement states that "to enhance the quality of educational activities and to nurture a culture of continuous improvement in all the academic undertakings within Bayero University, Kano." It was also part of the CDA's tripartite activities of training, research and outreach.

The workshop was a step-down training in view of the fact that the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello had last year approved 20 staff to go to University of Copenhagen for a training on innovative university teaching. The trainees were also trained in Abuja in the second phase to prepare for the train-the-trainer workshop in BUK.

"This is the third phase of the innovative teaching training. In April 2018, 20 academic staff from various departments participated in a training on **Innovative University Teaching, Learning and Supervision** in the

University of Copenhagen, Denmark, while the second phase of the training was conducted in December last year in Abuja," said the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello during the opening session of the workshop.

"The objectives of the workshop were to build the capacity of staff on modern pedagogy and effective supervision of students and improve the learning outcome by fostering critical thinking and adoption of improved teaching methods," said the Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin.

The Director gave a further background to the workshop, told the participants that the 20 staff trained on modern pedagogy in Copenhagen were mostly from the Faculty of Agriculture and other key faculties of the University including the Academic Planning Directorate.

"The training emanated from the need for the Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture to improve the way it delivers instructions to students, but being not in an island by itself, any improvement in the centre must also resonate to the rest of the University to be sustainable. The Vice Chancellor fully supported the idea and sponsored 20 of us to participate in the train the trainer course. We are to train staff who will later train other staff of the University. This is an important process in evolution of how we will improve teaching in the University,"

said the Director of CDA.

The workshop was all encompassing as the trainers provided platforms for presentations, practical sessions and interactions among the participants. One of the key resource persons at the Denmark training had monitored the training from Abuja through Skype.

The participants were introduced to the concept of Teaching Using Video (Screencast-O-Matic) by Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin. They were made to understand how to make and record lectures by themselves using software which is to be used for later presentation to students. It can even be used in the absence of a lecturer. Through practical sessions, the participants were taught how to log on to website and download the software to their laptops which is then used to create videos for their lectures.

One interesting thing to note is that the participants had all used the software and created short videos which were

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demonstrated during the week-long training period.

The participants were evaluated by the Copenhagen University through an online test to assess their level of understanding of the training.

At the end of the training, the 20 staff who received training in Denmark last year received their certificates brought from Copenhagen, Denmark.

Topics covered during the train-the trainer workshop included: Constructive Alignment; Inquiry Lesson Example + Extraction of 5E+F; Creating Intended Learning Outcomes; Discussion on Microteaching; Planning Micro-Teaching; Integrating Dialogue into Teaching; IT-based Students Response System and Research Based Teaching.

Others were Test and Measurement; Large Class Activation, Teaching Using Video (Screencast-O-Matic); Teaching Visitation; Leading and Implementing Change and Course Evaluation.

